

The holy spring of St. Regisse

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Like many phenomena in Denmark, the holy springs seem to be an intricate mixture of probably pre-Christian roots in viking age society, and perhaps before, paired with a heavy dose of medieval traditions from the era of catholicism and finally also the influence of the whole post-medieval era of Lutheran protestantism. However, the phenomenon of holy springs in the medieval era and before have been studied much too little, in Denmark, which is probably due to the massive lack of sufficient source material. It is really only during the Renaissance era and later, i.e. after the Reformation, when we begin to encounter a somewhat comprehensive source material on this phenomenon. As there were hundreds of such holy springs scattered across Denmark, the number of such springs is simply much too great to make an entry on all of them. This entry will thus take a look at one of the most famous and well-known holy springs in Denmark, while hoping that shedding light on this one holy spring will in the end also be a useful reflection of this phenomenon as a whole. The oldest written source mentioning the existence of a holy spring in the Frørup area dates from 1496, and this is probably the oldest written evidence of the existence of the holy spring of St. Regisse. Having actual medieval written evidence of the existence of this holy spring is an unusual luxury compared to most other holy springs in Denmark, something which participates in setting this holy spring apart and making the holy spring of St. Regisse particularly interesting as a case study. Further evidence of the state of this holy spring during the late medieval period can be garnered from a 1994 excavation. Late medieval pottery and coinage as old as the 1400s and 1500s was found here together with many pieces of medieval bricks and roof tiles. These latter findings were important documentation to back up the information provided by the oldest written source actually describing the place in details. Roughly 40 years after the Reformation, a man called Jacob Madsen became bishop of Odense diocese in Denmark. As part of his job he travelled widely around his diocese and in 1589 he visited the holy spring of St. Regisse and described the place in details in his note book based on what he saw himself and on what he was told by the local people. According to him, St. Regisse was a young woman who had been murdered here on this spot by some magnate, and the spring had apparently appeared here after the murder. At the time of Jacob Madsen, this holy spring was still, apparently, an intensely popular site of pilgrimage attracting people who believed that the water of this holy spring had healing powers. It can also be deduced from his 1589 description that he saw the ruins of a medieval chapel building whose demolition therefore must have been begun already before 1589. The last few ruins of the chapel were removed only in 1914/1915 by a local farmer. Had the chapel building itself been made surplus by the Reformation, when this location had stopped being part of the official church, the water and its supposed healing powers were still extremely sought after by pilgrims, at the time of Jacob Madsen. Jacob Madsen describes an extremely active site of pilgrimage. A second description of the site was provided by a local priest, Bendix Hansen, roughly 3 decades later, in 1623. Bendix also gives the impression of an extremely active pilgrimage site with a footpath leading up to it and people leaving crutches and similar here. The holy spring of St. Regisse actually kept its popularity as a site of pilgrimage, amongst people seeking the powers of the healing water, right up until the late 19th C. The chapel itself seems to have been a late medieval brick building probably dating from roughly the 15th C. Inside the chapel an image of St. Regisse could be seen, according to Bendix Hansen, and mass and sermon used to be held here annually (i.e. before the Reformation). By 1589 the place was also still surrounded by some kind of fence, according to Jacob Madsen. This seems to have been a fence of granite boulders whose last remnants apparently still existed by 1915. The fence was probably a leftover part of the late medieval appearance of the site. A lot of big

stones were also found here in the 1994 excavation. While there are no preserved medieval sources leaving any information on the chapel building, it is a possibility that there was some kind of connection between the chapel site and the local village church in Frørup. At least, the local Frørup church is very likely to have benefitted from the pilgrimage somehow. As it is still partially preserved, Frørup church is known to have possessed a so-called christ's tomb in the middle ages. All things considered, such a piece of late medieval inventory seems very far from being standard inventory across the village churches of late medieval Denmark. While it is very common that Danish village churches were expanded during the late middle ages, the church in Frørup seems to have been expanded quite heavily ending up in a size probably unusually large when compared to many other Danish village churches. It is known that pilgrimage to this site was still taking place by 1878, but that it died out soon after that sometime before 1885. Even after this time, it may still have continued for a while, though, on a smaller and less systematic scale and perhaps in a changed form. Overall this corresponds quite well with the general impression that such pilgrimage to the holy springs across Denmark seems to have died out roughly around 1900. By 1945 and 1965 stories of the pilgrimage to the holy spring of St. Regisse could still be told by some.

Date Range: 1400 CE - 1885 CE

Region: Site of Frørup and the spring of St. Regisse

Region tags: Denmark

Site of Frørup and the spring of St. Regisse. The Spring is placed between the village and the creek.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Mogens Bo Henriksen: "Regisse Kilde ved Frørup. Om kombinationen af skriftlige, arkæologiske og hellige kilder", Nyborg Før og Nu, 2002, p. 3-30

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: not relevant

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: It was excavated in 1994 (see article by Henriksen 2002).

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1994

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: as referred to in the article by Henriksen 2002

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Water source

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Clearing

– Water feature

– Other [specify]: Clearing and leveling of ground is likely to have happened when the medieval chapel was built.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: and the part in front round (as it looks nowadays)

–Other [specify]: and the part in front round (as it looks nowadays)

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

–Other [specify]: water

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: The medieval chapel was simply demolished over time, after the Reformation, as the bricks were probably reused elsewhere for other purposes. The remains of the post-medieval features of the place were "destroyed" in 1903 when a drastic rebuilding of the features was carried out.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For religious reasons

– For economic reasons

– For political reasons

– Other [specify]: The medieval chapel was destroyed after the Reformation when it was gradually torn down during the 16th century. Visible ruins were probably still present by 1589. On the surface this demolition could be defined as both religious and political reasons as it was caused by the Reformation making the cults of saints obsolete and inappropriate in the Lutheran church. Below the surface, however, the actual demolition was probably caused much more by merely practical concerns, i.e. economic reasons: during the middle ages, the financial foundation of the chapels at the holy springs seems to have been the pilgrimage and search of healing connected to the cult of saints. When the cult of saints was no longer part of the official church, the chapels at the holy springs lost their economic foundation of existence. All medieval chapels at the holy springs across Denmark thus had now become obsolete (as they were no longer used officially by the church for masses etc.), and it was, therefore, simply too expensive to maintain an unnecessary building and the bricks and stones could therefore be better reused for other purposes. While a great many medieval catholic churches were generally reused by the Danish Lutheran church after the Reformation, this does not go for the medieval chapels at the holy springs which were all torn down rather quickly. The main reason for this probably being simply the location: these holy springs and their chapels were generally situated in the midst of nature or in rural areas where there was simply no continued need of such an extra church building after the Reformation.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Other [specify]: none of the above

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

Notes: The structures of the place seems to have changed over time. In the medieval period, the place must have been dominated by a chapel building. This chapel was demolished in the 16th century, but pilgrims still continued travelling to the spring in search of its rumoured healing powers. Too little research has been into what the place looked like during the post-medieval period, but its features could very well have changed more than once during this period - as the site during this period seems to have been dominated by the pilgrims and not been systematically governed by an administrative power.

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: The answer is actually yes and no at the same time. The medieval chapel has not been reconstructed since it was demolished in the 16th century. However, the structures connected to the actual holy spring was renovated in 1903 so heavily that this work could be called a reconstruction. Most agree, though, that the work of 1903 was carried out in a manner less than successful.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although the costs necessarily involved with the building of the demolished medieval chapel clearly suggest that some sort of local power structure is highly likely to have been involved.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No information is preserved on the building process. The building of a medieval chapel, however, does suggest that pilgrimage to the site must have been rather extensive during the late medieval period. Such widespread pilgrimage obviously must have garnered an extensive local income

from it. It, therefore, seems quite likely that it was the income from the pilgrimage together with some sort of support from local power structures that made the building of the chapel possible.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: According to legend, as retold by Jacob Madsen, the holy spring suddenly appeared on the same spot where a young woman called Regisse had been murdered by a nobleman.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The apparent unjust murder of a woman believed to be innocent.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No information is preserved on the building of the medieval chapel, but the costs necessarily involved with the building process suggest that unknown financial support from some sort of power structure is likely to have been involved.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: People must have believed that the spring appearing on the same spot where Regisse had been murdered was God's sign that she was innocent and the murder was unjust. The spring was therefore thought to be holy and widespread pilgrimage to the site therefore began, as people believed the water to have healing powers.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: Although the medieval chapel ought to have been so at least to a certain extent

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Notes: Today: no monumental architecture is preserved. In the middle ages, however: yes, the medieval chapel would probably have fulfilled the criteria of definition as monumental architecture.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

|

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: stones shaped by humans

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: concrete (as of today, i.e. since the changes of 1903).

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Notes: Nowadays: no. Demolished medieval chapel: unknown.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Notes: No iconography is preserved. Bendix Hansen tells that the chapel used to contain an image of Regisse depicting her standing with her hand under her cheek as a sadly crying woman. Whether his words can be trusted is anyone's guess. However, the existence and use of a medieval chapel certainly does suggest that there would have been some iconography in the demolished medieval building before the Reformation. The image described by Bendix Hansen could have been some kind of altarpiece, but conclusions are uncertain.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Notes: No, but legend has it that the spring appeared because of the murder of a young woman.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: Before the Reformation, when the chapel existed and the place was part of the official church: yes, in the sense that the chapel should be regarded as an active ecclesiastical building used actively for ecclesiastical purposes. After the Reformation: probably no, in the sense that the chapel had been closed and the place had stopped being part of the official church, and focus of the people was now on the supposedly holy, healing powers of the water.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Notes: Before the Reformation when the chapel existed and the place was part of the official church: likely yes. It is likely that there would have been some sort of iconography within this chapel. After the Reformation, when the place had ceased being part of the official church: no. It does not seem so.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

Notes: Nothing is known as for exact numbers of people and such. Thus it is a case of how exactly the difference between small-scale and large is defined. As this was merely one amongst many such holy springs both before and after the Reformation, I have chosen to call it small-scale, but this answer could be debated.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Field does not know exact numbers, but it seems that it must have been quite popular already before the Reformation and that it continued to be so even the Reformation.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Annually. In the middle ages, when the chapel existed and the place was part of the official church: according to Bendix Hansen mass and sermon was held in the chapel annually on "Boelsmessedag" (i.e. 17th June). After the Reformation, when the location had stopped being part of the official church: mass and sermons were no longer held here, but people kept seeking the spring on a specific date after the Reformation. Apparently it just evolved into becoming the Saint John's Day (midsummer, i.e. 23th June) instead of 17th June.)

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

– No

Notes: Before the Reformation, when the place was part of the official church: perhaps yes. After the Reformation: No. The people kept seeking this place. It was not part of the official church any longer.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, e.g. in the sense that after the Reformation it is described as common practice that people left crutches etc. here.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Notes: Perhaps yes in the last period of its active existence, when focus had apparently stopped really being on healing any longer, but had now evolved into becoming instead perhaps almost a sort of a local public rejoicing instead.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Notes: Candles were left hanging in the trees. Money (coins) were thrown into the well. Sticks, crutches, and rags etc were left here by the visitors to the spring.

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

Notes: Not necessarily mandatory as it was never part of the official church after the Reformation, but it seems to have been very common amongst the people who visited the spring in hope of benefitting from the supposed healing powers of its water. What exactly traditions were regarding such holy springs, and as for this place in particular, before the Reformation is far more uncertain. During the 1994 excavation, however, the oldest coin found here dated from the 15th C. and late medieval pottery from the 15th and 16th C. was found here also.

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Some of them, yes (coins).

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: as described above

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Notes: It does not seem so. After the Reformation the location was not even part of the official church anymore. Before the Reformation, during the late medieval period, it seems that pilgrimage here must have been quite popular, but there is no evidence to support that it was ever mandatory.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Notes: Before the Reformation: obviously, maintenance of the chapel must have taken place, but no sources are preserved to tell us anything about the details.

↳ Is it required:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: After the Reformation when the place was no longer part of the official church: there does not seem to be knowledge of any systematic maintenance by any administrative powers. It seems that it must have been the visitors to the spring running the place primarily.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

Notes: No certain knowledge on this. It must be supposed that it was optional after the Reformation - as the location was not part of the official church anymore. As for during the late medieval era, it is unknown, but it could be guessed that optional was the most during the middle ages too.

Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The pilgrimage here during the middle ages must have been the very thing which resulted in the building of the chapel. Without pilgrimage here there would have been no need of building such a chapel. The pilgrimage was probably also the main thing paying for as well. Even after the Reformation pilgrimage was the main reason that the place kept existing.

Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Yes

Birth

– No

Transition to adulthood

– No

Death

– No

Other

– Other [specify]: After the Reformation: Sickness and health problems, i.e. the wish of benefitting from the supposed healing powers of the water. Before the Reformation: perhaps something similar, it could be guessed, but essentially it is unknown.

Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: To the extent possible: probably yes. Regarding the maintenance nothing is known for certain, but to some extent it should probably be expected that systematic pilgrimage to such extent must have roads and maintenance necessary.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Notes: After the actual pilgrimage to this place has died out, which happened between c. 1878 and 1885, it seems that the annual visits to the spring perhaps continued on for yet another few years, but in a changed form which perhaps also moved away from this exact location. As of 1893 there is a description of something more akin to an annual market with women baking cakes and a tent for dancing. However, this seems to have died out as well within a number of years.

Are festivals present:

– No

Notes: Not as such, no, but descriptions of the annual visits to the spring by healing-seekers on Saint John's Day during the post-Reformation era sometimes does make them seem rather like festivals

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– No

↳ Cleansing

– No

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: People sought the spring and the water for the healing powers it was thought to possess.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: The answer is actually yes and no at the same time. Before the Reformation, when a chapel was present here and annual masses were (apparently) held, obviously, religious specialists would have been present here part time in order to carry out such masses and make the chapel function. After the Reformation, when the chapel was demolished and masses were discontinued, pilgrimage to the site continued to take place, but religious specialists were no longer present. Bendix Hansen, as a Lutheran priest, was clearly uncomfortable with such customs continuing to take place in his area, but the desire of the people to seek the healing powers of the water, apparently, were so strong that authorities failed to stop the pilgrimage to this site even though, according to Bendix Hansen, they had actually tried.

↳ Present full time

– No

↳ Present part time

– Yes

Notes: The answer is both yes and no at the same time (cf. note).

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Talking about the middle ages, it would probably have been male priests here.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: Most likely Danish.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No details are preserved of any of the priests known to have been (apparently) active here during the middle ages.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

Notes: Unknown, but not necessarily. There have never been a monastery or anything like that on this site.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Notes: The hierarchy among the priesthood active here would expectedly have followed the normal hierarchy within the medieval church.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Before the Reformation: probably yes (to some extent). It is unknown, as no sources on this are preserved, but the presence of a medieval chapel suggests a connection between this place and some sort of local power structures and/or, probably also, some unknown branch of the church in the area. After the Reformation: No. It was the hope of the apparent healing powers of the water which made the people on an overtly unofficial level continue to make pilgrimages to this site. It was no longer guided, managed or officially supported by authorities.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Notes: But the building of a medieval chapel does suggest that some sort of formal bureaucracy must have been present during the middle ages. For the most part this must have been discontinued in its old form after the Reformation when the chapel was closed. However, people continued to travel to the site in hope of benefitting from the apparent healing powers of the water here. To some extent local power structures thus also appear to have continued to have some lesser degree of bureaucracy in place here even after the Reformation due to the continued income from the pilgrimage.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No information is preserved, but the building of a medieval chapel suggest that the place must have been connected to local power structures somehow.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

Notes: Although "yes" in the sense that the main reason that pilgrimage continued here for so long was that people hoped to benefit from the healing powers that they believed the water to have. Such healing powers could also be regarded as a service to the community of some sort.

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: According to Bendix Hansen, mass and sermon used to be held here annually on 17. June (i.e. until the chapel was apparently closed after the Reformation). This could also be regarded as a service to the community of some sort.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Notes: Not as far as we know. It could have been the case in the medieval chapel, of course, as some

amount of documents and records etc connected to the medieval chapel are likely to have existed, but it may have been stored somewhere else, es e.g. in the medieval institution or church that the medieval chapel is likely to have been connected to.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: Although scriptures of some sort must have been used and read here during the middle ages -if it is true that mass and sermon was held in the chapel annually.

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